

LONG-TERM STRATEGY TO OPTIMIZE RES PENETRATION IN ISOLATED GRID

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a techno-economic analysis of an isolated hybrid electrical system consisting of conventional Internal Combustion Engine(s) (ICE) and Renewable Energy Sources (RES) such as Wind Turbines (WT) and solar PhotoVoltaic (PV) panels. Actual plant configuration was defined based on real data from the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) installed at Ikaria Island, Greece. Optimization of the operational strategy is conducted by the Multi Energy Dispatchment Optimizer (MEDO), developed by the TPG group at the University of Genoa. The optimization algorithm is based on the Mix Integer Linear Problem (MILP) approach, and to account for the non-linear operating curve behaviour in off-design conditions for each technology, the piecewise linearization methodology has been adopted. In view of the growing interest in renewable energy production to reduce environmental impact, a scenario analysis has been carried out. In this scenario, the installed capacity of the Solar-PV panels and the WT is optimized, identifying the best share between solar and wind production based on Environmental and Economic parameters (annual production, fuel consumption, RES Energy Curtailment, CO₂ emissions cost, overall Levelized Cost Of Electricity (LCOE) and RES Energy share) identifying the best path towards an increase in RES penetration. This analysis has been conducted for two main scenarios: i) Operation of the island of Ikaria non-interconnected with nearby islands and in the absence of dedicated storage; ii) Optimal use of the existing Pumped Hydro Storage (PHS) for the non-interconnected island; several levels of grid security constraints were adopted to preserve stability. The introduction of PHS technology increases the RES penetration potential RES by significantly reducing the level of curtailment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Despite the global efforts towards high RES penetration, more than 60% of the electricity worldwide is still produced by the combustion of fossil fuels (*Carbon Dioxide Emissions From Electricity - World Nuclear Association*, n.d.)(IEA Electricity 2024: Analysis and Forecast to 2026, 2024). This high reliance on conventional power plant technologies is due to their superior reliability, flexibility and stability. The energy sector produced 37.7 gigatonnes of CO₂ emissions in 2023, which is 85% of the total global CO₂ emissions. This energy-related CO₂ emission is 1% higher than in 2019 (World Energy Outlook 2024, 2024). In particular, electricity generation is responsible for over 40% of energy related CO₂ emissions, the prime driver of climate change (*Carbon Dioxide Emissions From Electricity - World Nuclear Association*, n.d.). Fortunately, the fossil fuel share is expected to decline to 54% in 2026 (IEA Electricity 2024: Analysis and Forecast to 2026, 2024), and electricity related CO₂ emissions are expected to decline at an unprecedented average rate of 4% between 2023 and 2026 (IEA Electricity 2024: Analysis and Forecast to 2026, 2024). At the same time, global electricity demand continues to grow annually, rising by 2.2% in 2023 compared to 2022, and is projected to accelerate further over the next three years (IEA Electricity 2024: Analysis and Forecast to 2026, 2024). Consequently, the demand

for natural gas is expected to increase annually by 2.5% over the next decade (World Energy Outlook 2024, 2024).

Renewable energy has witnessed remarkable growth in the last couple of decades, and investments in clean energy projects are approaching USD 2 trillion each year (World Energy Outlook 2024, 2024). More than 560 GW of new renewable capacity was added in 2023 (World Energy Outlook 2024, 2024), and renewable power generation capacity is expected to increase from 4,250 GW today to around 10,000 GW in 2030 (World Energy Outlook 2024, 2024). It is worth highlighting that for the first time in 2019, electricity production from RES grew at a higher rate than that from conventional plants (*Renewables – Global Energy Review 2019 – Analysis - IEA*, n.d.). Specifically, solar-PV production increased by about 130 TWh or 6.5% in 2019 (*Renewables – Global Energy Review 2019 – Analysis - IEA*, n.d.). As a result of such advancements and regulatory incentives, the cost of utility-scale PV technology has declined by 82% since 2010 (Feldman et al., 2021). However, the penetration of high RES volume is challenging due to their variability, weather dependence, site dependence and non-programmability (Bird et al., 2016) and it can lead to grid operational constraints (Bird et al., 2016). Excess renewable energy during periods of low demand and challenges related to transmission and balancing supply and demand lead to renewable curtailment (Bird et al., 2016; Burke & Malley, 2011). Thus, significant global efforts are underway to store and reuse renewable energy via dispatchable generation (Schöniger et al., 2021)(Denholm & Mai, 2019).

An optimized hybrid solution comprising renewables, conventional plant and storage systems capable of providing a reliable and flexible strategy for large-scale power dispatch has gathered significant research interest in recent decades (Arefin & Das, 2017; Ding et al., 2019; Parthasarathy & Narayanan, 2014; Rashid et al., 2019a). A study by Ding et al. showed that a hybrid wind-solar plant coupled with a solar thermal storage system can reduce annual CO₂ emission by 15,470 tonnes compared to conventional coal plants (Ding et al., 2019). Moreover, using an electric heater in the thermal storage system reduces the curtailment and improves stability. Sioshansi et al. studied the energy deployment strategy of a hybrid wind and solar Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) plant and highlighted the potential benefits of the combined plant in terms of capacity factor and transmission rate due to the synergistic effect of real-time availability of the two resources (Sioshansi & Denholm, 2013). This is due to the different wind and solar generation profiles (i.e., not peak production at the same time). Similarly, Rashid et al. reported a greenhouse gas reduction of up to 23.78% in a natural gas plant hybridized with a parabolic trough solar collector (Rashid et al., 2019b). In this paper, two 140 MW plant configurations, one hybridized at plant level and another at the grid level, were compared with the standalone natural gas-fired plant. The results showed a high synergistic effect of hybridization at the plant level as compared to the grid level.

Renewable production is even more important for grids in decentralized or remote, non-interconnected island areas. In these areas, electricity generation often suffers from a higher cost regarding machinery, infrastructure, labour and fuel, which makes conventional generation less economical and designates renewables as a more cost-efficient option (Arefin & Das, 2017; Parthasarathy & Narayanan, 2014). Arefin et al. studied an 8.7 kW wind-diesel system on an Indonesian island and reported a 32.45% annual cost reduction and a 29-ton cut in CO₂ emissions (Arefin & Das, 2017). Rashid et al. studied the dispatch of a PV-wind-diesel hybrid system on a Bangladeshi island, demonstrating a 67% reduction in CO₂ emissions with 67.3% renewable energy generation at a cost of \$0.393 per kWh (Parthasarathy & Narayanan, 2014). Thus, deploying renewable energy on islands or isolated grids can lead to greater growth and reduce costs for renewable technologies. Recently, Dubey et al. studied island energy dispatch on the Canary Islands with conventional ICE, gas turbines and innovative gas turbines in the presence of a high share of solar PV (Dubey et al., 2025). The study showed that with a high solar PV share, the net efficiency of the hybrid plant decreased due to the higher part load operation of conventional generators, and ICE provided more economical solutions than gas turbines despite the high capital expenditure (CAPEX) of the ICE. Moreover, a larger number of small-sized generators was found to deliver higher net power plant efficiency than large-sized generators (Dubey et al., 2025).

In this paper, the optimal transition path towards higher RES share is presented, optimizing the dispatch of a hybrid power plant on an island consisting of conventional ICE generators and renewables, namely solar-PV, wind and pumped hydro storage. Section 2 of the paper describes the reference scenario of Ikaria Island, providing an overview of the current generation system. Then, the piecewise linearised MILP model, developed to account for the non-linear behaviour of the off-design curves of the ICEs,

is introduced. Finally, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis is presented to characterize the system and provide grid operators with more insight to define the optimal strategy for planning the installed RES capacity.

2 METHODOLOGY AND CASE STUDY

In Section 2, the authors first focus on describing the reference scenario of the island of Ikaria, providing an overview and characterization of the current power generation system. The section then presents the piecewise linearised MILP model developed to account for the non-linear behaviour of the off-design curves of the ICEs. A constant efficiency assumption has been considered for the pumps and hydraulic turbines. Finally, sensitivity analysis is conducted to thoroughly characterize the system, providing grid operators with deeper insights to determine optimal strategies for planning RES capacity installations.

2.1 Ikaria Island Scenario

The Ikaria's electrical energy demand, which is managed by the internal energy system, experiences fluctuation between 2 MW and 8 MW during different periods of the year. In Table 1 and

Table 2, the off-design curves are reported for the main production units of the Ikaria grid (Malamaki et al., 2024; Papaefthymiou et al., 2010a). These off-design curves were used to develop the MILP model of the Ikaria Island power system. The respective generation facilities include a conventional Autonomous Local Fuel Power Station (ALFPS) consisting of 9 heavy fuel oil (mazut/diesel) ICE with a total capacity of 15.6 MW. The system has a total installed WT capacity of 3.6 MW, divided into two wind plants of 0.9 MW and 2.7 MW. The most flexible component is the PHS, which consists of three reservoirs, two-generation power stations with hydraulic turbines with a total output power of 4.6 MW, and a pumping station at the lowest reservoir with a total absorbed power of 3 MW. Reservoir 1 (Pezi) is a natural reservoir with a total capacity of 900,000 m³. The hydroelectric unit for this reservoir can be used only in winter and spring; only a surplus of water is used for power generation, while in summer, the reservoir is used only for irrigation and water supply. The actual PHS plant is composed of Reservoir 2 (Proespera) and Reservoir 3 (Proespera Kato), with a capacity of 80,000 m³ each. These two reservoirs are hydraulically connected by a double penstock system, ensuring that generation and pumping operations remain independent for higher operational flexibility. Hydro units 1 and 2 have a rated power of 1.55 MW each and are used for the PHS system. The pumping station, located at Kato Proespera, comprises eight fixed-speed pumps (FSPs) of 250 kW each, controlled by a soft starter, and four Variable-Speed Pumps (VSPs) of 250 kW each. The VSPs are prioritized for operation, while the minimum pump load is 50%, equivalent to 125 kW. When wind potential is available, the WT and pumping station operate in tandem to pump and store water as hybrid energy in the reservoirs. This process effectively converts intermittent wind energy into stored hydraulic energy, which is then used to generate hydroelectric power to meet the demand load. Further details of the system components can be found in (Papaefthymiou et al., 2010a; Papakonstantinou et al., 2023).

Table 1: Internal Combustion Engine off-design performance used for the MILP model

ALFPS N°	SFOC gr/kWh			Efficiency [%]			Power [kW]		
	50%	75%	100%	50%	75%	100%	50%	75%	100%
ICE ₁	235.7	226.5	224.3	36.80	38.30	38.67	1750	2625	3500
ICE ₂	235.7	226.5	224.3	36.80	38.30	38.67	1750	2625	3500
ICE ₃	235.7	226.5	224.3	36.80	38.30	38.67	1450	2175	2900
ICE ₄	245.4	225.8	220.9	35.35	38.42	39.27	1100	1650	2200
ICE ₅	255	239	237.5	34.02	36.30	36.53	375	562.5	750
ICE ₆	255	239	237.5	34.02	36.30	36.53	375	562.5	750
ICE ₇	255	239	237.5	34.02	36.30	36.53	375	562.5	750
ICE ₈	255	239	237.5	34.02	36.30	36.53	375	562.5	750

ICE₉ 267.5 252.6 246 32.43 34.34 35.26 375 562.5 750

Table 2: Hydro Turbines and Hydro Pumps off-design performance used for the MILP model

PHS Plant	Mass Flow Rate [m ³ /h]			Efficiency [%]			Power [kW]		
	N°	10%	50%	100%	10%	50%	100%	10%	50%
HT	136.2	627.3	1235.1	82.0	89.0	90.4	150	750	1550
HP	153.0	791.1	1610.4	70.9	73.3	74.6	300	1500	3000

To highlight the impact of the new renewable capacity integration into the system, Reservoir 1, located in Pezi, was neglected, as it only provides energy for a specific period, and its operation is prioritized for irrigation and water supply needs. In the developed model, only Reservoir 2 and Reservoir 3 were considered for the PHS. Thus, the optimizer respected the operational and security constraints of the network. For the electricity grid security and operational continuity, it is necessary to introduce two constraints related to the minimum baseload guaranteed by programmable load technologies. These two constraints are formulated in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2. The first constraint requires a minimum amount of energy to be supplied by ICE at each optimization hour. Based on historical data acquired within the EU SINNOGENES project (Sinnogenes, 2022), the C_1 value was set at 20%. The second constraint defines a minimum required energy that must be provided by both the ICE and the Hydro Turbines intended for use in the Pumped Hydro Storage (PHS); based on historical data, it has been observed that the C_2 value should be at least 60%. The optimization is conducted for a year, with hourly granularity.

$$SR_1 = \frac{E_{ICE_t}}{E_{D_t}} \cdot 100 \geq C_1, \forall t \in [1, 8760] \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$SR_2 = \frac{E_{ICE_t} + E_{HT}}{E_{D_t}} \cdot 100 \geq C_2, \forall t \in [1, 8760] \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

2.2 Piecewise MILP optimization approach

Non-linear functions, such as normalized efficiency dependent on normalized power load, typically represent power system characteristic off-design curves. Non-linear curves can be approximated using piecewise linearization to simplify calculations and improve computational efficiency. This method involves segmenting the non-linear function's domain into multiple intervals and approximating each segment with a linear equation. By doing so, the piecewise linear model maintains a close approximation to the original function while leveraging the simplicity of linear formulations.

A common application of this technique is in the modelling of ICE, as Vasylyev et al. have already presented in their work (Vasylyev et al., 2024). The fuel consumption of an ICE is influenced by its power output, with not a constant slope due to the non-linear behaviour of the efficiency at different power loads. By employing piecewise linearization, the relationship between optimized power variables and the operational costs of the system can be effectively represented through linearised fuel consumption functions. To achieve an accurate linearised representation, an auxiliary variable defined as the “on-off_{ICE}” must be introduced. This variable is structured as a three-dimensional matrix indexed by i for the specific component, j for the linearised segment, and t for the optimized time step. The problem is formulated into the following equations:

$$P_{ICE_{min}}(i, j) \cdot onoff_{ICE}(i, j, t) \leq P_{ICE}(i, j, t) \leq P_{ICE_{max}}(i, j) \cdot onoff_{ICE}(i, j, t) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$\alpha(i, j) = \frac{\dot{m}_{fuel_{max}}(i, j) - \dot{m}_{fuel_{min}}(i, j)}{P_{max}(i, j) - P_{min}(i, j)} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\beta(i, j) = \dot{m}_{fuel_{max}}(i, j) - \alpha(i, j) \cdot P_{max}(i, j) \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$\dot{m}_{fuel}(i, j, t) = \alpha(i, j) \cdot P_{ICE}(i, j) + \beta(i, j) \cdot onoff_{ICE}(i, j, t) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\eta(i, j) = \frac{P_{ICE}(i, j)}{\dot{m}_{fuel}(i, j) \cdot LHV} = \frac{P_{ICE}(i, j)}{(\alpha(i, j) \cdot P_{ICE}(i, j) + \beta(i, j)) \cdot LHV} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

From Eq. 3 to Eq. 7, a detailed formulation of the linearised function for the ICE model is provided. Eq. 3 defines the operating limits of the optimized function P_{ICE} , ensuring that it remains within the defined linear range of the system. Eq. 4 and Eq. 5 define the coefficients used for the piecewise linearization of the fuel consumption of the ICE model, considering its operating conditions.

It is important to emphasize that α and β are two-dimensional parameters, as they are specific to a given ICE model and a given linearised segment. However, for P_{ICE} , a third dimension is introduced to account for its variability over the optimized periods. Eq. 6 establishes the relationship between the fuel consumption and the operating state of the ICE. Finally, Eq. 7 determines the efficiency of the ICE. Although this variable is not directly included in the objective function (to avoid non-linearity, making it incompatible with the MILP approach), the efficiency calculation for the linearised approach is used to verify the validity of the model after optimization to compare with the actual off-design curve.

The objective function ($Obj_{function}$) has two main terms: one for the fuel consumption cost (Ω_{HFO}) and the other for the CO₂ emissions cost (Ω_{CO_2}). The fuel consumption cost is calculated in Eq. 8 with a heavy fuel oil (HFO) price of 0.53 €/kg and is assumed to remain stable throughout the year (*EMEA Bunker Prices, 2024*). The CO₂ emission cost is calculated in Eq. 9 via emission factor (EF_{HFO}), which indicates the average amount of carbon dioxide released per tonne of HFO burned. This factor is then multiplied by the fuel consumption rate (\dot{m}_{HFO}) and the applicable carbon tax (Tax_{CO_2}). The emission factor for HFO is assumed to be 3.15 ton_{CO₂}/ton_{HFO} (*Marine Benchmark, 2020*), while the carbon tax is set at 70 €/ton CO₂ (*Sendeco2, n.d.*). The entire optimization period of the year 2023 has been divided using the rolling horizon technique. The study of the importance of the choice of an appropriate simulation window (SW) for more efficient scheduling of storage systems has already been carried out in the following work (*Vasylyev et al., 2023*).

$$\Omega_{HFO} = \sum_{t=1}^{T=SW} \dot{m}_{HFO_t}^{tot} \cdot \Delta t \cdot C_{HFO} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$\Omega_{CO_2} = \sum_{t=1}^{T=SW} (\dot{m}_{HFO_t}^{tot} \cdot \Delta t \cdot EF_{HFO}) \cdot Tax_{CO_2} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

$$Obj_{function} = \min (\Omega_{HFO} + \Omega_{CO_2}) \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

2.3 Sensitivity Analysis

The objective of this work is to evaluate how an increased capacity of renewable energy can affect the operation of the grid electricity system on Ikaria Island. A two-scenario sensitivity analysis was defined for varying the installed capacity of photovoltaic panels and wind turbines; the capacity values considered for the sensitivity analysis are presented in Table 3. For scenario 1, with no PHS considered, three variations of SR_1 were considered (20%, 40% and 60%), as this parameter has a strong impact on the curtailment levels and RES penetration. For the second scenario, with PHS included, the analysis included only the WT and PV installed capacity, with SR_1 and SR_2 set to 20% and 60%, respectively.

Table 3: Wind and Solar installed capacity levels

Parameter	Installed Capacity Levels [MW]								
	0	0.4	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Wind	0	0.4	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Photovoltaic	0	1	2	3	3.6	4	5	6	7

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

In this section, Key Performance Indicators (KPI) are presented to compare different solutions and scenarios. Figure 1 illustrates the hourly energy balance for Scenario 2 with a total RES installed capacity of 6 MW (3 MW of Wind Turbines and 3 Photovoltaic Panels).

In the figure, the negative y-axis represents demand and pumped hydro storage charging, while the positive y-axis represents ICE, RES, and pumped hydro storage discharging. The black line on the y-axis indicates the sum of electricity demand and storage charging energy, a threshold above which RES energy cannot be absorbed, leading to energy curtailment. In Figure 1, the conditions of low and high RES production can be observed, facilitating a clear view of the operating conditions throughout the entire optimization year. The figure shows that even under high RES conditions, the minimum base load of ICE must be maintained to meet the security requirement SR_1 of 20%. In the high RES scenario, particularly during the 19th–20th of February, the system optimizes the operation of the pumped hydro plant to minimize ICE load, thereby reducing the specific cost per unit of energy produced.

Notably, at noon on 19 February, the high RES potential exceeds the demand and the capacity of the pumping station, resulting in energy curtailment. On days with low wind potential, the system compensates by increasing the share of energy generated by ICE, starting from the afternoon of 20 February. The planned pumped storage plant will play a crucial role in shifting RES production, significantly increasing RES penetration and reducing energy curtailment. The PHS system features two pipelines: one is used exclusively for the discharge phase, while the other serves the charging phases. This configuration ensures greater flexibility by separating the two phases. The needs of security requirements SR_2 drive this solution, even if there is a waste of energy due to the round trip efficiency.

Figure 1: Example of dispatch in Scenario 2 (with PHS): Electrical hourly energy balance for the Ikaria Island Grid, with a total RES capacity installed of 6 MW (3 MW of Wind Turbines and 3 MW of Photovoltaic Panels).

Four KPIs have been introduced to compare different scenarios of installed RES capacity. The KPIs characterize the electricity grid for different shares of renewable energy. These include two technical indicators ($E_{RES}\%$ and $E_c\%$), one economic indicator ($LCOE$), and one environmental indicator (SCI_D). In particular,

- ($E_{RES}\%$): The RES share indicator quantifies the share of total electrical Energy Demand E_D met by renewable energy sources, specifically WT and PV systems, for the scenario without PHS (i.e. Scenario 1), while for Scenario 2, the $E_{RES}\%$ also takes into account the energy provided by PHS, as charging energy is provided by the RES excess. In Eq. 11, the actual E_{RES} consumption is calculated as the difference between the total electrical energy demand E_D and the total electrical energy supplied by the ICE, E_{ICE} , weighted by the total E_D for the entire year.

$$E_{RES}\% = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} (E_{D_t} - E_{ICE_t})}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{D_t}} \cdot 100 = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{RES_t}}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{D_t}} \cdot 100 [\%] \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

- ($E_c\%$): The RES Curtailment indicator evaluates the grid's ability to absorb the available renewable energy, highlighting the extent to which excess energy from RES cannot be utilized due to system constraints. The RES curtailment is calculated in Eq. 12 as the difference between the available renewable energy and the actual renewable energy used, weighted by the total RES energy available throughout the year.

$$E_c\% = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} (E_{RES_t}^{available} - E_{RES_t})}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{RES_t}^{available}} \cdot 100 [\%] \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

- ($LCOE$): The Levelized Cost of Electricity is an economic indicator that compares different scenarios based on their financial impact. For this assessment, only the CAPEX of the newly installed RES capacity is considered, as conventional technologies are already in place. In Eq. 13, the Capital Recovery Factor CRF_j is defined for the WT and (PV) systems; i_{rate} is the interest rate equal to 5%, n is the useful life span of each system (n_{WT} 27 years; n_{PV} 25 years). The specific capital cost for the WT was considered to be 1.11 M€/MW (Jørgensen et al., n.d.) and for the PV panels, 0.56 M€/MW. CRF_j coefficient enables the total CAPEX investment costs to be annualized, allowing for a consistent assessment of both system operating costs OPEX and investment costs on the same time basis. The LCOE, i.e., the specific cost of electricity, taking into account the total annual costs, is given in Eq. 14.

$$CRF_j = \frac{i_{rate} \cdot (1 + i_{rate})^n}{(1 + i_{rate})^n - 1} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

$$LCOE = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} (OPEX_{ICE_t}) + CRF_{WT} \cdot CAPEX_{WT} + CRF_{PV} \cdot CAPEX_{PV}}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{D_t}} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{MWh} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

- (SCI): Specific Carbon Intensity is an environmental indicator that measures the specific CO₂ emissions to provide a unit of energy. The Specific Carbon emission reduction is related to the ability to substitute traditional fossil fuel production with renewable energy. Due to the Safety Grid Requirement (SR₁ and SR₂), there is a limitation on the achievable maximum reduction.

$$SCI = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} CO_{2_t}}{\sum_{t=1}^{8760} E_{D_t}} \left[\frac{ton}{MWh} \right] \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

3.2 Techno-economic and Environmental results

The following section presents and discusses the results using the KPIs defined in the previous section. First, technical parameters such as RES share ($E_{RES}\%$) and RES curtailment ($E_c\%$) are presented. These parameters are evaluated in relation to both the installed capacity and the potential annual energy of WT and PV.

Next, the economic parameter Levelized Cost Of Electricity ($LCOE$) is analysed, also taking into account the level of curtailment, as this represents an inefficiency in the system's ability to absorb the total renewable potential.

Finally, the discussion focuses on the evolution of the environmental parameter, Specific Carbon Intensity (SCI), once again taking into account curtailment levels.

Figure 2: Renewable Energy Sources Share and iso-Curtailment levels for different Installed Capacities levels for Wind Turbines (x-axis) and Photovoltaic panels (y-axis). (a-c) Scenario 1 SR_1 (60%, 40% and 20%), (d) Scenario 2 SR_1 20%; SR_2 60%.

Figure 2 presents the RES share ($E_{RES}\%$) as a function of the installed capacities of WT and PV, while RES curtailment ($E_c\%$) levels are represented as contour lines in red to improve readability. The black line facilitates the determination of the optimal installed capacity of WT and PV to ensure a given RES share with the least curtailment. From Figure 2, it can be observed that for high SR_1 values in Scenario 1, there are significant challenges in increasing RES share, leading to a sharp rise in curtailment levels. In the worst-case scenario (Figure 2a), the maximum $E_{RES}\%$ reaches 35%, while $E_c\%$ is 75%. By reducing SR_1 values, it is possible to achieve a maximum RES share of 65% and $E_c\%$ of 52.5%, ensuring lower security requirements (Figure 2c).

In Scenario 2 (Figure 2d), the significant benefits of PHS can be observed, as it helps maintain security constraints at actual working levels while improving RES integration, reducing the RES curtailment strongly. It is worth noting that in Scenario 2, for a capacity range of 3 MW of WT nominal installed capacity to 4.5 MW of PV nominal installed capacity, the curtailment is less than 1%, ensuring a maximum RES penetration of 50%. This indicates a system capable of efficiently absorbing all renewable production. For a 3 MW WT capacity, it can be seen that a RES share value of 50% can be achieved. However, to exceed this threshold while minimizing $E_c\%$, a significant amount of PV capacity needs to be installed. A more balanced distribution between the two installed capacities is then restored. The maximum $E_{RES}\%$ is 70%, while in that condition the minimum $E_c\%$ is 35%

It can be noticed that at the beginning of stable curtailment occurrence (5% for Scenario 1 and 1% for Scenario 2), the optimal ratio between installed WT and PV capacity is approximately 2. This effect is mainly due to longer operating hours (the WT are producing 90% of the hours vs 50% of the PVs) and a higher capacity factor of up to 57% vs 20% more than compensating for the higher CAPEX. When curtailment starts, the addition of capacity is shared among WT and PV, with a still not completely clear saw-tooth pattern. When the curtailment grows, the contribution of the PV capacity increases up to roughly a 1:1 ratio. In fact, under high curtailment conditions, the decoupling effect between the production profiles of the two different RES sources becomes predominant over time.

Figure 3 illustrates the trends for RES share and RES curtailment, but this time as a function of the annual renewable energy potential. This visualisation clearly shows that small variations in installed WT capacity lead to significantly higher energy production.

Hence, increasing the installed PV capacity is less beneficial under certain conditions, as its capacity factor is much lower, up to 20%, due to the inherent nature of the energy source. When a stable curtailment is achieved, the production from the WT in the ideal condition is up to 5 times the PV one. It can be seen that the reduction of the backup grid requirements and the use of PHS in Scenario 2 allows an increase in the amount of energy produced by the PV panels as a result of the storage mitigating the peak shaving effect.

Figure 3: Renewable Energy Sources Share and iso-Curtailment levels for different Available Energy for Wind Turbines (x-axis) and Photovoltaic panels (y-axis). (a-c) Scenario 1: SR_1 (60%, 40% and 20%), (d) Scenario 2: SR_1 20%; SR_2 60%.

Figure 4: Levelized Cost of Electricity ($LCOE$) and iso-curtailment levels for different Installed Capacity for Wind Turbines (x-axis) and Photovoltaic panels (y-axis). (a-c) Scenario 1: SR_1 (60%, 40% and 20%), (d) Scenario 2: SR_1 20%; SR_2 60%.

Figure 4 presents the Levelized Cost of Electricity ($LCOE$) behaviour within the installed RES capacity range investigated. As expected, compared to an $LCOE$ of 150 €/MWh when only ICEs are adopted, the introduction of the RES generators with their lower nominal $LCOE$ has a beneficial effect. When curtailment becomes significant, the resulting $LCOE$ from RES starts growing since the additional CAPEX is not compensated by a proportional production.

It is worth noting that a curtailment limit, around 55% in all scenarios, is observed, beyond which further increases in RES share are no longer economically profitable. This is because the higher initial investment costs outweigh the benefit of the additional RES share. In Scenario 1 (Figure 4 a-c), the maximum achievable $LCOE$ reduction is limited to about 21% for highest SR_1 due to the low flexibility capability of the system to manage periods of excess RES production, while for the lowest SR_1 , the maximum reduction is considerable up to 48% but with a strong reduction in the reserve capacity.

In contrast, Scenario 2 (Figure 4d) achieves a significant reduction in $LCOE$, from a maximum of 150 €/MWh in the absence of RES to 70 €/MWh at maximum installed capacity, a reduction of 53%. This significant reduction results from the fact that the PHS plant is already in place, and no additional investment is required. It is noted that, despite lower security in Scenario 1 with $SR_1 = 20\%$, results close to those of Scenario 2 can be achieved if only $LCOE$ is considered, with a difference of approximately 7.75 €/MWh. This difference is entirely attributable to the system's reduced capability to absorb RES production peaks, resulting in higher curtailment levels.

Figure 5: Specific Carbon Intensity and iso-curtailment levels for different Installed Capacity for Wind Turbines (x-axis) and Photovoltaic Panels (y-axis). (a-c) Scenario 1: SR_1 (60%, 40% and 20%), (d) Scenario 2: SR_1 20%; SR_2 60%.

Figure 5 presents the fourth indicator considered, namely the Specific Carbon Intensity (*SCI*). *SCI* is represented within the domain of installed RES capacities. In Scenario 1, with no RES capacity installed, emissions reach almost 700 kg/MWh, primarily due to ICEs operating at an average efficiency of around 38% (Papaefthymiou et al., 2010b).

Unlike the economic indicator (LCOE), the environmental one (*SCI*) consistently decreases by an additional installation of RES capacity because every increase in RES share reduces the capacity factor of ICEs, which in turn results in lower emissions.

With a higher SR_1 value (Figure 5a) and maximum installed RES capacity, *SCI* decreases to approximately 500 kg/MWh, representing a 28% reduction. Conversely, for minimum SR_1 (Figure 5c), *SCI* is even lower, with a reduction of around 57%.

In Scenario 2 (Figure 5d), a significant reduction in *SCI* is observed even for low installed power levels, reaching a maximum reduction of 64%. Once again, for equal WT and PV installed capacity, there is no significant variation in *SCI*. This is due to both the low capacity factor and the fact that PV generation is concentrated in certain time slots.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the complex trade-off between installed RES capacity, system flexibility and economic and environmental performance of hybrid systems (composed of fossil and renewable sources). The analysis showcases that there are significant challenges to the increased RES penetration, especially for Scenario 1 with high Security Requirements (SR_1), where Heavy Fuel Oil should provide 60% of the hourly demand fed I CEs.

For Scenario 1, with an SR_1 of 20%, a curtailment of 5% is reached with an installed capacity of 1 MW WT and 0.4 MW PV, resulting in a 20% RES penetration. A minimum of overall production cost is identified at 55% curtailment with an LCOE of 117.5 €/MWh for a 3 MW WT and 2 MW PV installed capacity. In these conditions, the resulting specific carbon intensity is equal to 500 kg/MWh, with a maximum reduction of 28%. For Scenario 1 with $SR_1 = 20\%$, a curtailment level of 5% is reached with an installed capacity of 2 MW of WT and 1 MW of PV, achieving a maximum RES share of 40%. Under these conditions, LCOE is 100 €/MWh, representing a 30% reduction compared to the complete absence of RES capacity, while SCI reaches 450 kg/MWh, reflecting a 35% decrease. The minimum LCOE of 77.5 €/MWh was achieved with a curtailment level of 35% and an installed capacity of 4 MW of WT and 3.5 MW of PV. Under these conditions, SCI was 300 kg/MWh, representing a 57% reduction.

The introduction of PHS (Scenario 2) plays a crucial role in reducing curtailment and improving system flexibility, allowing a higher share of RES with minimal energy curtailment. This condition is particularly evident in the 3 MW WT - 4.5 MW PV capacity range, where curtailment drops below 1%, ensuring efficient use of high RES share up to 50% for 3 MW of WT and 1.5 MW of PV installed capacity. In these conditions, the SCI is 350 kg/MWh with a significant reduction of 35%. The minimum LCOE achieved is 70 €/MWh, with an installed capacity of 5 MW of WT and 5 MW of PV and a curtailment level of 25%. Under these conditions, SCI is 250 kg/MWh, reflecting a 50% reduction.

Analysing the optimal transition path towards higher RES share, it can be noticed that this parameter is optimized in the absence of curtailment by a ratio of WT over PV capacity of about 2, resulting in an energy production ratio among the two sources of around 5. The minimum LCOE was found for all the scenarios when 55% of curtailment is reached for a ratio of WT over PV capacity of about 1.5. Beyond this limit, additional RES capacity becomes economically unviable due to increasing investment costs. The results suggest that in Scenario 1, the maximum cost reduction is limited (21% for high $SR_1 = 60\%$), while a more flexible approach (low $SR_1 = 20\%$) allows a reduction of up to 48% at the expense of reducing reserve capacity. In scenario 2, the presence of PHS reduces the LCOE by 53%, demonstrating the economic advantage of integrating energy storage solutions.

In addition, the analysis of the annual renewable energy potential (Figure 3) confirms that WT plants provide a higher energy yield per unit of installed capacity due to higher operating hours and capacity factors, while PV expansion is less effective under certain conditions due to its inherent intermittency. From an economic perspective (Figure 4), the study identifies a curtailment threshold of around 55%. The environmental analysis (Figure 5) further confirms the benefits of RES integration, showing that CO_2 emissions (SCI) can be reduced by up to 64% in Scenario 2, even with low RES capacities. In Scenario 1, emissions fall by 28% at high SR_1 and 57% at low SR_1 , reflecting the limited flexibility of the system without storage. The results also confirm that merely PV installation and operation does not have a significant impact on emission reduction, as the capacity factor remains low and generation is concentrated in specific time slots.

In conclusion, the results highlight the importance of system flexibility in enabling a higher RES share with less curtailment and improved economic viability. The integration of PHS establishes it as a key enabler to achieve significant cost reductions and emissions savings, making it a valuable strategy to increase the uptake of renewable energy in power systems.

Future work will address the effect of uncertainty in the production and demand profiles on the optimal transition path.

5 NOMENCLATURE

Acronyms

ALFPS	Autonomous Local Fuel Power Station
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
FSP	Fixed-Speed Pumps
HFO	Heavy Fuel Oil
IEC(s)	Internal Combustion Engine(s)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LHV	Low Heating Value
MEDO	Multi Energy Dispatchment Optimizer
MILP	Mixed Integer Linear Programming
PHS	Pumped and Hydro Storage
PV	Photovoltaic Panels
RES	Renewable Energy Source
SFOC	Specific Fuel Oil Consumption
VSP	Variable-Speed Pumps
WT	Wind Turbine

Symbols

E_C	RES Energy Curtailment [%]
E_D	Demand Electrical Energy [kWh]
E_{HT}	Hydro Turbine Energy [kWh]
E_{ICE}	Internal Combustion Engine Energy [kWh]
E_{RES}	RES Energy Share [%]
i_{rate}	Interest rate [%]
LCOE	Levelized Cost Of Electricity [€/MWh]
m_{fuel}	Fuel Consumption [kg/kWh]
onoff	Binary on-off variable [-]
P_{ICE}	Internal Combustion Engine Optimized Power [kW]
SCI	Specific Carbon Intensity [ton _{CO2} /MWh]
SR	Security Required Constraint [%]
α	Slope coefficient for piecewise linearization
β	Constant coefficient for the piecewise linearization
η	Efficiency [-]
Ω	Cost Function [€]

Subscripts

i	i^{th} Modeled Component
j	j^{th} Linearized piecewise segment
max	Maximum value of the j^{th} linearized piecewise
min	Minimum value of the j^{th} linearized piecewise
t	time step [h]

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